

E-Learning to go

Module 2 - Unit 11 e-Learning Tools

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Where we are in our process or e-learning tool box !

What is an LMS?

- Learning Management System, generally addressed as LMS system makes advanced training easy and accessible.
 - LMS is an application that can be deployed for the administration, management, and delivery of educational programs, training programs, or development programs.
 - On any device, you can create, distribute, and track from anywhere by making use of LMS.
- **Recent studies indicate that by 2026, the market of global corporate learning management system is expected to reach over \$370 billion** (Statista 2020)

- LMS covers almost all the major markets like schools, educational institutions, corporate, medical industry, etc. It becomes handy in identifying the communication gap between the instructor and the learner by checking each individual's progress on quizzes and assessments.
- Learning online becomes more fun with video tutorials, stories, and features like gamification, etc.
- LMS has changed the learning perspective of every individual across the globe. It has provided a wide scope for the users to choose and learn in whichever field they want to excel, as all the information can now be shared across the globe.

Let us investigate this more in detail...

LMS Market Facts

10 LMS Statistics You Need to Know in 2021

- By 2026, the global eLearning market is forecasted to reach over **\$370 billion** (Statista 2020)
- **98% of educational institutions** moved the majority of their classes to online courses as of April 2020. (Education Data 2021)
- **77% of learners** feel that their LMS has had a positive impact on satisfaction, productivity, and teaching during COVID-19. (Capterra 2020)
- **64% of global L&D pros** agree that learning & development shifted from a “nice to have” to a “need to have” in 2021. (LinkedIn 2021)
- **23% of companies** have been using the same LMS for over five years. (Docebo 2019)
- **39% of users** consider functionality as the most significant priority when selecting a new LMS. (Capterra 2020)
- **99% of institutions** provide LMS and educational technology support for students, but a majority of students have either not received any LMS training or don't know if they have received training. (EDUCAUSE 2020)
- **33% of global L&D pros** surveyed in March 2021 expect their budgets to increase. Only 19% expect their budgets to decrease. (LinkedIn 2021)
- Google Classroom commands **39% of the LMS market** in 2021 when compared to other leading LMS software. (TrustRadius 2021)

LMS Usage Statistics

- **77% of higher education faculty** agree or strongly agree that the LMS is critical to their teaching. 73% believe the LMS is a critical tool to enhance student learning. (EDUcause 2020)
- **68.3% of higher education students** used the LMS for all of their courses. (EDUcause 2020)
- Although **99% of institutions** provide LMS and educational technology support for students, a majority of students have either not received any LMS training or don't know if they have received training. (EDUcause 2020)
- **89% of higher education faculty** already used some of the features of the LMS before the COVID-19 pandemic (mainly for administrative tasks such as posting a syllabus, pushing out information, pushing out and collecting assignments, and tracking grades). (EDUcause 2020)
- Before the pandemic, **38% of higher education faculty** across institution types used the LMS to teach completely online courses. That number was highest among AA institution faculty (52.3%) and lowest among BA faculty (25.4%). (EDUcause 2020)
- **35.9% of students** at associate-level institutions have received formal LMS training—which is more than students at other types of institutions. (EDUcause 2020)
- **23% of companies** have been using the same LMS for over five years. (Docebo 2019)
- **39% of users** consider functionality as the most significant priority when selecting a new LMS. The other considerations focused on reliability (20%), training support (17%) as well as price (12%). (Capterra 2020)
- **Poor usability (53%) and high cost (44%)** were seen as the biggest factors that cause learning leaders to seek out a new and improved learning management system. (Capterra 2020)

Where is LMS used?

- You will find one or the other connection of LMS in the respective industry which you are looking for. Any individual who adopts online learning uses an LMS.

LMS is used by:

- Almost all Corporate and organizations.
- All Educational institutions (Schools & Universities).
- Many government companies.
- Private institutions.

What purpose does LMS solve?

- LMS is a platform that is open for individuals and professionals to learn and display their skills.
 - it is administered centrally by IT or the teacher
 - It is filled with content by the teacher or the teachers
 - It allows addition of material of the participants
 - It allows communication, evaluation and data storage
- In LMS, we can create
 - learning programs,
 - courses,
 - multiple LMS content
 - embed external content
 - tutorials
 - Etc. and
- post them so that anyone can enhance their skill set with those materials.

LMS provides an all-in-one platform for learning and upgrading the skill set.

Advantages & Disadvantages of LMS

Advantages

- Learning Management System helps to streamline the learning pattern which in turn saves time for the instructors so that they can utilize that time to focus more on each individual's progress.
- Everything becomes digital, hence it saves a lot of money on buying notebooks, copies, etc.
- As things become digital, learning becomes more interesting with the existence of video tutorials, clips, gamification, etc.
- All documents and media are stored at one place
- It gives the freedom to the user to learn from anywhere and thereby increases mobility.
- Easy effective management is possible with LMS and information accessibility becomes quick and accurate.

Though there are several advantages of LMS, there are certain limitations too.

Disadvantages:

- The impact of face-to-face interaction is reduced, as no gathering is required for learning.
- It increases the tunnel effect of learning, hence the scope of wide thinking may get reduced and the user may just see through LMS, thereby leaving many opportunities outside.
- Some students need motivation and encouragement to learn which will be missing and thereby credibility issues will be present.
- The biggest drawback of an LMS is, that you have to make yourself familiar with an extremely multifunctional tool! It needs time to get routine and to find the tools which fit best to you, your students and your teaching topic!

Higher Education Technology Landscape

EDUVENTURES
Evidence. Expertise. Impact.

...so many tools! What are to essential features of an LMS?

Essential LMS Features

Integrated virtual classroom

Enables learners to get into learning on each new e-course they sign up for.

Technical Support

Technical assistance is required when things go wrong,

Customizable & multi-lingual

As per the requirement the valuable pieces of software get customized

Course management

Semi-automatic course administration, order management, pre-registration, and assigning courses can be performed.

Reports

Customized reports help in tracking the learner and the tutor performance easily.

Communication Management

Within the LMS system, all course communications and notifications can be done.

SCORM compatibility

Wide range of different course types and formats in the e-learning industry to certify compatibility.

Data Storage

Make administration more comfortable to manage by securely keeping e-courses and training resources.

Assessment creation & management

Easy to create and manage the assessment tools.

Ecommerce

Direct payments through LMS make financial administration simple and straight-forward.

 GoodFirms

Open Source LMS Comparisson

Software	Platform	Academic/ Education	Asynchronous Learning	Blended learning	Gamification	SCORM Compliance	Video Conferencing
Moodle	Cloud, SaaS, Web, Mac, Windows, Android Native, iOS Native	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
TalentLMS	Windows, Android, iOS		✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
FormaLMS	Cloud , SaaS, Mac,Windows	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ILIAS	Cloud, SaaS, Web	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Opigno	Cloud, SaaS, Mac, Windows, Android Native, iOS Native	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
OpenOLAT	Windows, Linux, macOS	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Sakai	Cloud,SaaS, Web, windows, iOS Native	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
Dokeos	Cloud, SaaS, Web, Android Native iOS Native	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Not fulfilled

Moodle: one, if not the leading LMS!

Moodle LMS

Empowering educators to improve our world

☆☆☆☆☆ 0.0 (0 Review)

Moodle is the world's most trusted online learning solution. The engine of the Moodle ecosystem is Moodle LMS, the secure and customisable open-source platform used by over 250 million learners worldwide. Developed in conjunction with its loyal community, Moodle LMS is complemented by an ecosystem of products including Moodle Workplace and a network of partners and services providing hosting, cu... [learn more about Moodle LMS](#)

VISIT WEBSITE

Free Trial

Available

Entry Level Price

Free version

Add to Compare

Write a Review

Characteristics of the Moodle LMS

7 Advantages of Moodle relevant for us teachers

And this is all for Free! Moodle is an Open Source Solution!

Summary of Moodle features

- Moodle stands for "Modular Object Oriented Dynamik Learning Environment".
 - 200 million users
 - LMS market share in Europe, Latin America & Oceania of 50%.
 - Moodle the most used LMS in the world.
- Is an Open Source Solution
 - Available free of charge
 - highly flexible and customizable
 - eager community and therefore countless guides, tutorials, plugins, etc.
 - 1800 plugins and more!
- Uncomplicated but at first also a bit hard to get used to
 - Moodle needs and deserves a little leap of faith from you!
 - Some things are unintuitive at first but you will see: Moodle can do an incredible amount and sets you hardly any limits!

Let us see, how we can work with Moodle!

How does Moodle work?

Moodle is like a platform that you can work with in any way and in a very flexible way

- Managed by your Moodle administrators

A wide variety of courses can be created on this platform

- Courses are created by your Moodle administrators or you (depending on permissions)

Courses can be designed with a wide variety of activities & materials

- Takes place through the lecturers & teachers

Number & combination possibilities of activities & materials

- Lecturer decides, based on the didactic concept and own goals, quite flexibly

Moodle Standard Activities

- Are automatically installed in the Moodle system
- With these activities & materials you already get very far!

Moodle Plugins

- Additionally more than 1800 freely available plugins for design, activities, functions, reports etc.
- Easy to install by your Moodle administrators

Moodle Standard Activities 1/2

An **ACTIVITY** is something that a student will do that interacts with other students and or the teacher.

There are 14 different types of activities in the **standard Moodle** that can be found when the editing is turned on and the link 'Add an activity or resource' is clicked.

- Assignments
 - Enable teachers to grade and give comments on uploaded files and assignments created on and off line
- Chat
 - Allows participants to have a real-time synchronous discussion
- Choice
 - A teacher asks a question and specifies a choice of multiple responses
- Database
 - Enables participants to create, maintain and search a bank of record entries
- External tool
 - Allows participants to interact with LTI compliant learning resources and activities on other web sites.
- Feedback
 - For creating and conducting surveys to collect feedback
- Forum
 - Allows participants to have asynchronous discussions

Moodle Standard Activities 2/2

An **ACTIVITY** is something that a student will do that interacts with other students and or the teacher.

There are 14 different types of activities in the standard Moodle that can be found when the editing is turned on and the link 'Add an activity or resource' is clicked.

- [Glossary](#)
 - Enables participants to create and maintain a list of definitions, like a dictionary
- [Lesson](#)
 - For delivering content in flexible ways
- [Quiz](#)
 - Allows the teacher to design and set quiz tests, which may be automatically marked and feedback and/or to correct answers shown
- [SCORM](#)
 - Enables SCORM packages to be included as course content
- [Survey](#)
 - For gathering data from students to help teachers learn about their class and reflect on their own teaching
- [Wiki](#)
 - A collection of web pages that anyone can add to or edit
- [Workshop](#)
 - Enables peer assessment

**This is only the standard initial installation!
Remember: more than 1800 more plugins!**

Moodle Standard Ressources

RESOURCES are generally static information that a teacher wants the students to read or watch, such as a file or link.

- Moodle supports a range of resource types which teachers can add to their courses. Resources appear as a single link with an icon in front of it that represents the type of resource. In edit mode, a teacher can add resources via the 'Add an activity or resource' link.
- [Book](#) - Multi-page resources with a book-like format. *Teachers can export their Books as IMS CP* (admin must allow teacher role to export IMS)
- [File](#) - A picture, a pdf document, a spreadsheet, a sound file, a video file
- [Folder](#) - For helping organize files and one folder may contain other folders
- [IMS content package](#) - Add static material from other sources in the standard IMS content package format
- [Label](#) - Can be a few displayed words or an image used to separate resources and activities in a topic section, or can be a lengthy description or instructions
- [Page](#) - The student sees a single, scrollable screen that a teacher creates with the robust HTML editor
- [URL](#) - You can send the student to any place they can reach

Let us get a first impression about some
ACTIVITIES and RESOURCES live in Moodle!

Let us try to cluster ACTIVITIES & RESOURCES

Communicate

Forum, announcement, chat, etc.

Store

Deploy files, videos, interactive videos, SCORM packages, etc.

Evaluate

Tests, exams, interactive content, H5P, peer assessment, etc.

Collaborate

Grouping, Tasks, Wiki, Equitable Distribution, Glossary, etc.

Aktivität oder Material anlegen

Suchen

Alle Aktivitäten Arbeitsmaterial

Aufgabe ☆ ⓘ	BigBlueButton ☆ ⓘ	Buch ☆ ⓘ	Datei ☆ ⓘ	Datenbank ☆ ⓘ	Externes Tool ☆ ⓘ
Feedback ☆ ⓘ	Forum ☆ ⓘ	Gegenseitige Bearbeitung ☆ ⓘ	Gerechte Verteilung ☆ ⓘ	Glossar ☆ ⓘ	Gruppenwahl ☆ ⓘ
H5P ☆ ⓘ	IMS-Content ☆ ⓘ	Interaktiver Inhalt ☆ ⓘ	Lektion ☆ ⓘ	Lernpaket ☆ ⓘ	Link/URL ☆ ⓘ
Test ☆ ⓘ	Textfeld ☆ ⓘ	Textseite ☆ ⓘ	Umfrage ☆ ⓘ	Verzeichnis ☆ ⓘ	Wiki ☆ ⓘ

In "my" Moodle from E-Learning to go installed plugins!

Moodle Plugin Directory

Assessment Plugin type (any) More

What are you looking for? Search

Sort by Relevance Sites Downloads Fans Recently updated Recently added

1926 plugins 1061 devs 352.1K recent downloads

NAVIGATION

- Startseite
- Website
- Communities
- Plugins
- Plugin reviews
- Statistics
- Reports
- Plugin types

Game

The game activity module makes use of questions, quizzes and glossaries to create offer a variety of interactive games.

ReadAloud by Poodll

ReadAloud measures reading speed and accuracy without creating extra work for teachers. AI auto-grading and robust HTML5

STACK

The STACK question type adds a sophisticated assessment in mathematics and related disciplines, with emphasis on formative

Open Badge Factory

Issue Open Badges created in Open Badge Factory from Moodle, and display badges issued to users.

OneNote submissions

This plugin allows students to work on an assignment in OneNote. This includes creating a OneNote page associated with an

OneNote Feedback

This plugin allows teachers to grade and providing feedback for OneNote assignment submissions. This includes viewing a student's

Let us review live how to find plugins!

...how to start with Moodle – from Standard to Expert Mode!

Course examples

www.e-learningtogo.de

Preparation Questions (Homework - workload target 60 minutes)

Prepare yourself for our lecture by creating for yourself an overview about existing Open Educational Resources and databases providing them

1. For example here you do find databases like this:
 - <https://oerworldmap.org/resource/?language=en&filter.about.additionalType.%40id=%5B%22https%3A%2F%2Foerworldmap.org%2Fassets%2Fjson%2Fpublications.json%23oer%22%5D>
 - <https://www.oercommons.org/>
2. You are you using already OER?
 1. If yes please describe briefly in PPT which resources you do use and how your experience is!
 2. Do you plan to use further OER? If yes please describe them as well briefly.
 3. If time allows you will be invited to present our experience regarding OER.
3. You have not used OER until now, please make yourself familiar with existing databases and
 1. choose at least 2 OER which you plan to use in the upcoming semester
 2. Please describe them briefly in PPT and explain how you plan to implement them in your teaching concept
 3. If time allows you will be invited to present our experience regarding OER

There is more external content to be found: OER
it's your turn!

What is an E-Learning Authoring Tool?

- An elearning authoring tool is a software program that enables users to create learning content, lessons and courses using text, media, and interactions. Mainly such content developed to use it in LMS and can be saved in various formats.
- A user does not actually need any technical programming expertise to utilize the software.
- Instead, elearning authoring tools are generally pre-programmed and offer a ready-to-use interface complete with templates, media, tools, interactions, and tests that the user can easily arrange and manipulate.

How do authoring tools work?

- No two content authoring tools are alike. Created by different software companies, there are a wide variety of program options that cater to different elearning needs.
- Some programs are geared towards non-specialists who require rapid elearning development and just want to utilize pre-made templates for simple content, interactions and quizzes, while other programs are geared towards specialists who want to develop highly customized content, such as adaptive learning experiences, simulations or custom gamification.
- Despite the variation available in features and functionality, authoring tools all perform the same overall function: they create elearning courses for an end-user audience by way of content creation, content organization, and content standards.

Authoring tool Features & Capabilities

Let's take a look at some major authoring tool capabilities and the specific features that they offer:

- Content authoring
- Interactivity
- Templates and theme
- Content management
- Collaboration
- Assessment
- Accessibility
- Publishing
- Administration
- Support & Training

**In other words...all you need for E-Learning!
What is Moodle then for? Hosting of SCORM!**

- The core feature of any authoring tool is the ability to create lessons.
- This includes adding and editing slides, images, text, video, audio or any other on-screen element.
- These features will enable you to bring your course to life and represent what the learner will be seeing, hearing, and doing.

➤ Let us review some Highlights!

Content authoring with Authoring Systems

- The kind of e-learning course that you create depends on these core content authoring features:

- **Images**

- Add or import images
- Edit images

- **Audio**

- Import and export audio files
- Edit audio files
- Record audio for narration
- Include audio files in on-screen interactions

- **Video**

- Webcam recording
- Screen recording
- Import and export videos
- Insert videos to interactions
- Link to external video sources
- Edit videos

- **Animations**

- Animate on-screen images or text
- Ability to import Flash animations
- Ability to import HTML5 animations
- Ability to insert text animations

- **Formatting**

- Text & style editing
- Object alignment & editing
- Background themes
- Create master slides
- Navigation player skin options
- Page transitions
- Responsive design
- Importing a PowerPoint lesson

Interactivity, Tests & Quizze

- An e-learning that engages a learner by having them actively participate in the course involves a host of interactive features.
- Interactivity can help increase learner engagement and retention by enabling the learner to take a more active role in acquiring information; this can be through the discovery of information, solving a problem, or working through scenarios.
- Here are some major features that improve interactivity:
 - Built-in activities: drag & drop, matching, hotspot reveal, sliders, or dials
 - Create custom activities or games
 - Create interactions or character scenarios with on-screen objects or images by:
 - Slide layers
 - States
 - Triggers
 - Pop-ups
 - Variables
 - Markers
 - Buttons
 - Scrolling panels

GIW 2 - Chapter 2.5 Friction

Print Page Downloads User Manual Contact Problem Collection Exit Course

Quiz

hochschule aschaffenburg
University of Applied Sciences

Friction

Objects in contact on horizontal surface

Please assign the correct "Behaviour text" to the free body diagram by dragging and dropping from the left to right!

Behaviour "Drag here"	Behaviour "Drop here"	Free Body Diagram
No friction, ($P_x = 0$)	Drop correct text here	$N = P + W$ Click on image to enlarge and right click to shrink
No motion, ($P_x < F_{max}$)	Drop correct text here	$F = P_x$ $F < \mu_s N$ $N = P_y + W$
Motion, ($P_x > F_{max}$)	Drop correct text here	$F_m = P_x$ $F_m = \mu_k N$ $N = P_y + W$
Motion impending ($P_x = F_{max}$)	Drop correct text here	$F_k < P_x$ $F_k = \mu_s N$ $N = P_y + W$

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Quizzes and tests with an E-Learning Authoring Tool

- E-Learning Authoring Tools offer a big variety of different quiz types.

- As the E-Learning SCORM Package (the E-Learning Course produced with an E-Learning Authoring Tool) communicates with Moodle it is possible to generate reports and exams.-
- Points or Gradings from most different exercises can be added up and those are reported finally to Moodle
- Communication from Moodle to the SCORM Package (e.g. importing names of Students) is possible as well.

My clear recommendation is nevertheless to realize exams in the LMS as e.g. Moodle and not in an E-Learning Authoring System!

Further Features

- **Standard templates and themes:** Whether you have specific organizational branding or you just need to find a consistent look and feel, the theme capability of an authoring tool will help you establish the right design for your course.
- **Content management:** It is important to be able to organize your assets, media and other content.
- **Collaboration:** Collaboration features enable you to quickly and easily share an e-learning with whoever else might need to see it or work on it.
- **Assessment:** Assessment features help determine what your learner has retained in the course, enables a way to track learner achievement and progress, and also helps you to determine the effectiveness of the course.
- **Accessibility:** In order to respect the different audio-visual sensory needs of individuals, accessibility features can change or add on-screen elements, interactions and formatting in order to suit different audience needs. (may be organized in Moodle as well)
- **Administration:** Having the flexibility to set-up preferences and organize the workflow enables everyone to work in their own style.
- **Publishing:** Every organization has its own specific publishing requirement in order for an e-learning to be uploaded and made accessible for learners. Typically this is SCORM uploaded to a LMS as Moodle

What does SCORM compliant authoring tool mean?

- Most elearning authoring tools need to be compliant with content standards. This means that the course can be exported to a file type that will be compatible and supported by SCORM compliant LMS systems.
- For end-users to access a published course, the course needs to be located somewhere accessible - like the internet or an LMS. This is where content standards come in.

E-Learning Authoring Tools: A short list

- [Articulate Storyline](#) is online training software that helps you create online eLearning courses quickly and easily. Storyline is the eLearning authoring tool that grows with you, allowing you to start simply and work up to building highly interactive online and mobile courses.
- [Adobe Captivate](#) is a rapid responsive authoring tool that is used for creating elearning contents such as software demonstrations, software simulations, branched scenarios, and randomized quizzes in Small Web Formats (.swf) and HTML5 formats.

- Those 2 tools are the market leaders! Others, as for example Ispring do a good job as well.

In combination with Moodle and a video Tool like Camtasia Studio you can do really everything what can be desired in E-Learning

- [Camtasia Studio and Camtasia for Mac](#) are software suites, created and published by TechSmith, for creating video tutorials and presentations directly via screencast, or via a direct recording plug-in to Microsoft PowerPoint.
- Camtasia Studio consists of two major components:
 - Camtasia Recorder - a separate tool for capturing screen audio and video
 - Camtasia Studio editor – video post processing

- **My personal setup: Moodle + Articulate Storyline + Camtasia**

Let us review Storyline & Camtasia live to learn about the tools!

The screenshot displays the Articulate Storyline software interface. On the left, a navigation menu titled 'Menü & Suche' lists various video tutorial topics such as 'E-Learning Kurs BASIS', 'Videotutorials', and 'Anmoderation Gesamtkurs'. The main workspace shows a course titled 'E-Learning Kurs Basis' with a timeline and a storyboard. A green callout box with the text 'ON AIR Aufzeichnung Tonspur' is overlaid on the interface, indicating that the audio recording feature is active. The interface includes a top menu bar with options like 'E-Mail', 'Navigation', and 'Seminarbaukasten', and a toolbar with various interactive object tools. The storyboard content includes a slide titled 'Wichtige Grundfunktionen von Microsoft Outlook' with a diagram showing Outlook's main functions: E-Mail, Kalender, Aufgaben, and Kontakte.

Summary

- LMS Systems are extremely powerful and provide a huge quantity of tools to enable E-Learning
- One of the biggest LMS Tools is free of charge: Moodle
- A lot of content can be realized directly in the LMS System
- Additional content, basically based on your existing PPT Presentations can be much easier converted into E-Learning with an E-Learning Authoring Tool like Articulate Storyline
- To enrich the E-learning Courses with videos and screencast the usage of an external Video Software like Camtasia is recommendable. This makes working on the videos much easier in comparison to video processing in Moodle and/or Storyline

With a combination of an LMS like Moodle, an E-Learning Authoring Tool like Storyline and a Video Tool like Camtasia Studio you can do really everything what can be desired in E-Learning. This is exactly my recommended Setup!

Reflection Questions after Unit 11

(Homework - workload target 60 minutes)

Having seen concrete examples of E-Learning Course you are asked to reflect upon your own lectures.

1. Choose 4 of your lectures in a way that you can separate them in lectures
 1. where the content could be realized best with the LMS functions we discussed this session
 2. where the content could be realized best with an E-Learning Authoring Tool
 3. where the content could be realized best with a Video Tool (Screenrecording oder Explanatory Videos)
 4. where the content could be realized best with OER solutions
2. Give reason for the differences you made
3. Analyse which Open Source Video tools are on the market and which are recommendable. The usage is easier than you think!
 - They should offer Screenrecording, Video Post Processing and the production as .mp4 videos.
4. If you use actually an LMS, please make a hitlist of the 5 next functions you will realize in which courses. Please give reason for your choice.

Preparation Questions for Unit 12

(Homework - workload target 60 minutes)

Prepare yourself for our lecture by analyzing and summarizing the boundary conditions for e-exams and e-feedback at your home university

1. Analyze if your university LMS (Learning Management System e.g. Moodle) support tests and if yes which types of questions can be realized?
2. Does your university permit to install or is willing to install further types of questions (in Moodle called plugins) in addition to the standard questions?
3. Does your university LMS System offer something which is comparable to the „Safe Exam Browser“ in Moodle?
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ytztYguXixk>)
4. Investigate if there are already e-exams running at your university as best practice!
5. Please investigate how the regulations by law or by your university do look like regarding distance exams and online proctoring during distance exams.

FOR NEXT SESSION

E-Learning to go

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